

Studies on the photochemical interaction of Fuchsin Basic dye with Triton X-100

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Abstract : A new solarchemical cell consisting of Fuchsin Basic, a cationic triphenyl methane dye, and triethanol amine as reductant in solution of surfactant separated from a saturated aqueous solution of iodine by a pyrex sintered glass membrane, has been developed. The surfactants used was Triton X-100 (non-ionic). The results show that the photopotential and photocurrent of the cell is increased in Triton X-100 and decreased with the cell without surfactant. The photopotential and photocurrent of the cell were observed as 690 mV, 175 μ A respectively and power of the cell was 63.4 μ A/min. The possible mechanisms of the cell in the various surfactants are discussed.

Keywords : Fuchsin Basic, Triton X-100, triethanol amine, electrical performance.

Introduction

Surfactants are surface active agents, and are amphiphilic in nature, which can form an assembled structure like micelle or reverse micelle in aqueous and non aqueous solution, respectively¹.

Surfactant plays a vital role for conversion and storage for solar energy by stabilizing the photoproducts and decreasing the rate of back recombination reaction of the photo sensitizer compounds like organic dye molecules^{2,3}. The most outstanding properties of the surfactants are their ability to solubilize molecules which otherwise would not be soluble in water. Many dyes, polynuclear hydrocarbons, and proteins are stabilized in presence of micelles through displaying marked spectral and colour change⁴. An elegant approach for the storing light energy in an iron-thionine cell has been proposed⁵. The photoproducts are separated by solubilization of the reduced thionine in an ether layer in which the oxidized thionine is insoluble. The importance of organized molecular assemblies, such as micelles, bilayers and membranes, in controlling the course of chemical reactions, particularly those related to the problem of light energy conversion and storage, has been recognized⁶. The use of surfactant (micelles) to increase the photoinduced electrical parameters may involve the introduction of a spatial barrier to the back oxidation process. The addition of Triton X-100 micelles to an iron-thionine cell leads to an increased

solubilization of the dye, and an overall increase in conversion efficiency by a factor of 5 [7].

Srivastava *et al.*⁸ investigated the thionine-Fe^{II}, methyleneblue-Fe^{II} and riboflavinethylenediaminetetraacetic acid systems in polyvinylmethylether surfactant and found that the dye was incorporated in the hydrophobic core of the micelle, and the photopotentials generated remained steady for more than 48 h. Photoreduction processes have been investigated in various organized media, such as surfactant (micellar) solution or microemulsions, to achieve enhanced photochemical and photoelectrochemical effects⁹⁻¹¹. Dixit and Mackay¹² have found that the current and voltage responses of a totally illuminated thin layer photogalvanic cell, consisting of a newly synthesized thionine-surfactant complex (C₁₀ThH⁺) and Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ in a 60% microemulsion (anionic) medium, are enhanced, and the effect is larger in an anionic medium, than in Tween-80 and water.

Bowen¹³ has studied the PEC effect of sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS) on the thionine-Fe^{II} system, and has inferred that the addition of the micelle increases the rate of diffusion of the photoreduced species, reduces the formation of the destructive leuco dye and greatly increases the rate of its destruction, and leads to increased solubilisation of thionine. The photoreduction of thionine and methylene blue by ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) bound to anionic NaLS is inhibited due to the electrostatic re-

pulsion between the surfactant (micelle) and the reductant, but the photoreduction by EDTA of Eosine bound to a cationic micelle is enhanced¹⁴. Photoreduction processes have been investigated in the presence of micelles and organized systems by other workers to achieve an enhanced PEC effect¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

Use of micelles in solar energy conversion and storage were investigated by Gangotri *et al.*¹⁹. Studies of surfactant in photogalvanic cells was observed by Meena *et al.*²⁰ and role of reductant and photosensitizer in solar energy conversion and storage; oxalic acid - Brilliant cresyl system have been recently reported by Sindal *et al.*²¹.

The system consisting of Fuchsin Basic dye - TEA and Triton X-100 has been extensively studied in our laboratory and the system generates appreciable photovoltage and photocurrent when studied in a PG cell. The conversion efficiency of the system can be increased. Attempts have also been made to store the absorbed energy in this system by separating the anode compartment (containing Fuchsin Basic-TEA) from the cathode compartment containing a saturated aqueous solution of the electron acceptor (iodine) by a sintered glass membrane and in this way the absorbed energy can be stored for up to 3-4 days²². However, with anionic NaLS, the dye is held at the Stern layer because of coulombic interaction, and with Tween-80, there is no appreciable effect due to coulombic repulsion²³. In this paper, we present the effect of Triton X-100 surfactant in the Fuchsin Basic-TEA PG cell.

Experimental

Fuchsin Basic supplied by Sigma Chemicals, was recrystallized from an ethanol-water mixture. The surfactant Triton X-100 were of A.R. grade, supplied by B.D.H. iodine, supplied by E. Merck, was resublimated under

reduced pressure before use.

The cell employed to study the photogalvanic effect of the dye - EDTA-surfactants system has been described previously^{22,24}. The illuminated (anode) chamber consisted of a Fuchsin Basic-TEA-Triton X-100 system. In the surfactant concentration above and below the critical micelle concentration (CMC) and the dark (cathode) chamber consisted of an aqueous saturated solution of iodine, separated by a pyrex sintered glass membrane (porosity G-4).

The light source was a tungsten projector lamp (200 W) focused at an intensity of 10.4 mW cm⁻². The solution in the anode chamber was deoxygenated by bubbling with nitrogen gas. The photovoltages and photocurrents were measured using a Micrometer (OSAW, India). Photopotentials were measured using open circuit conditions.

Results and discussion

On illumination of the anode compartment of the cell, consisting of a deoxygenated aqueous solution of Fuchsin Basic-TEA with Triton X-100 nonionic surfactant, a photopotential develops and attains its maximum value (V_{oc}) within a few minutes. When the illumination is stopped, the generated photopotential gradually decreases and the time required to reach the original dark value is 3 to 4 h, however, decay time varies with the nature of the surfactant used.

On addition of the nonionic surfactant Triton X-100 to the cell below the CMC, there is an increase in V_{oc} . At the CMC, V_{oc} increase appreciably and there is a 37-fold increase in SEE compared with the cell containing only dye - EDTA²². Use of Triton X-100 above the CMC, leads to an increase in the storage capability and decrease in V_{oc} . The decay process takes 4-5 h compared with 3-4 h for the cell containing surfactant (Table 1, Fig. 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of the FB-TEA and Triton X-100 PG cell in the presence of Triton X-100 surfactants at 303 K different concentration of Fuchsin Basic are = 8.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³, 7.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³, 5.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, 3.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³

[Cathode compartment contains a saturated aqueous solution of iodine]

Surfactant	Concentration of surfactants (mol dm ⁻³)	V_{oc} (mV)	I_{sc} (μ A)	Fill factor (η)	Power of cell	$T_{1/2}$
Triton X-100	8.0×10^{-6}	690	175	0.31	63.4 μ A/min	60.0
	7.0×10^{-6}	550	155			min
	5.0×10^{-5}	378	138			
	3.0×10^{-5}	255	130			
	1.0×10^{-5}	218	120			

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram shows photovoltage and photocurrent of the solar cell containing different concentration of Fuchsin Basic dye. The concentrations are (in mol dm⁻³) : (1) 8.0 × 10⁻⁶, (2) 7.0 × 10⁻⁶, (3) 5.0 × 10⁻⁵, (4) 3.0 × 10⁻⁵, (5) 1.0 × 10⁻⁵.

Fig. 2. Current-voltage characteristics of photogalvanic cells containing a saturated aqueous solution of iodine in the cathode compartment and (1) FB-TEA-Triton X-100 in the anode compartment at 303 K. Concentrations of Fuchsin Basic are 8.0×10^{-6} , 7.0×10^{-6} , 5.0×10^{-5} , 3.0×10^{-5} and 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ respectively.

The current-voltage characteristics of FB-TEA in the presence of the Triton X-100 surfactant are shown in Fig. 2.

The steps that lead to photovoltage generation in the dye redox system are as follows¹⁹: the dye is excited to its triplet state (³D) which then undergoes protonation (³DH⁺ or ³DH₂⁺), followed by charge transfer interaction between the triply protonated dye and ionized TEA (HY³⁻ or Y⁴⁻). The reduced dye (DH⁺; semidye; the electroactive species as determined from flash photolysis studies on Fuchsin Basic)²⁵ is the charge carrier which diffuses to the illuminated electrode surface, and releases the electron to the electrode. This electron flows through the external circuit to the cathode compartment, reduces iodine to I⁻ which is oxidized again on the membrane behaves as a double electrode, undergoing oxidation on the cathode side (oxidation of I⁻ to I₂) and reduction on the anode side (reduction of the oxidized form of TEA).

An explanation for the increase in photoreduction on addition of surfactant has been provided by other workers. Groenen *et al.*⁷ have proposed that the addition of Triton X-100 above the CMC to the Fe^{II}-thionine system increases the efficiency compared with the cell free micelle due to the inclusion of leucothionine within the micelle. This causes a reduction in its diffusion towards the

electrode and hence enhances the photochemistry. Usui and Saga¹⁴ have reported that an enhancement of photoreduction occurs in their system due to the electrostatic attraction between the cationic micelle dodecyl trimethyl ammonium chloride (DTAC) and HY³⁻ and the cationic dye 10-dodecyl acidine orange (the dye is located on the surface of the micelle). However, the photoreduction of methylene blue bound to anionic NaLS is inhibited by EDTA because of the electrostatic repulsion between NaLS and EDTA. Spectroscopic studies reveal that PSF exhibits a charge transfer interaction with Triton X-100, the site of interaction being the polyoxyethylene chain. With NaLS, a coulombic interaction is observed and there is no interaction with CTAB²³.

On the basis of above results, our observations can be explained as follows.

FB-TEA-Triton X-100 system :

Although the FB-TEA and Triton X-100 system generates a large V_{oc} , the presence of Triton X-100 significantly increases V_{oc} . In this case, the dye is held at the Gouy-Chapman layer due to coulombic interaction, since FB exists as a positively charged species at the experimental pH (10.6). Micelle provide a stronger attractive barrier to the close approach of a negatively charged elec-

tron donor TEA, thereby enhancing the photovoltage of the system.

Conclusions :

From the above results, we can conclude that the addition of anionic and nonionic micelles to the FB-TEA-PG cell leads to increased storage and conversion efficiency of the cell.

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